

TEACHING ENGLISH THROUGH GAMES

Muhammadiyah Tursunoy
the student of

Termez Economics and Service University
Foreign language and literature

Scientific supervisor: Kodirova Sarvinovz Ravshanovna
the teacher of

Termez Economics and Service University
Foreign language and literature

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ABSTRACT

this article under discussion deals with English language teaching through games. Utilizing games in classroom can fulfill the essential aim of teaching, which to make students active participants in the learning process and keep them motivated. Moreover, this games can develop sense of creativity and curiosity. Nowadays, games are main section of English language learning. One of the pros of the games is all students work simultaneously. The utilization of numerous games helps to attract children to a foreign language, creates conditions for success in language learning. And students who want to play, will definitely want to improve their knowledge of a foreign language.

Introduction

Language is a tool of communication that is used to inform or ask other humans certain things, to express feelings, emotions, ideas or share knowledge or experiences. Definitely, language has a great importance since it serves linguistic communication, which is a basic need for society. In addition, learning new language gives the individual an excellent opportunity in today's reality.

Having knowledge of English multiplies your chances of getting a good job in your country, but also even abroad in international companies. English has become the language of many fields of today's world, such as science, aviation, technology, diplomacy, tourism and many others. Learning English serves for not only work, but also it is crucial as well on socializing and entertainment, since it is also the language of many social Medias nowadays¹.

Many children starting to learn a foreign language at school think it is fun. But after a while they begin to realize that is not easy at all, and soon the foreign language becomes one of the difficult subjects. One of the reasons that leads to this result is the desired result. Learning is more effective if students are actively involved in process.

There are various ways to encourage children to be active, but the most effective ones are playing games which develop creativity and curiosity. Nowadays, games are an integral part of English language teaching. Games contribute to intensive language practice. They can be used at the beginning of a lesson or at the end to stimulate, reduce tension after a test, to change activities in a lesson.

"A language -game is a philosophical concept developed by Lud Wittgenstein, referring to simple examples of language use and the actions into which the language is woven.

¹ Lukyanchikova N.V. Foreign language teaching at the initial stage of education //PRIMARY SCHOOL, 2001

Wittgenstein argued that a word or even a sentence has meaning only as a result of the 'rule' of the 'game' being played. Language itself is involved inside an activity to gain its meaning"²

It is important that the games bring joy and help to train language phenomena. One of the advantages of games is that all students work at the same time. Participation in games develops the ability to cooperate, to compete without aggression, to be able to lose, to take responsibility.

The games contribute to the following methodological tasks;

- Creation of children's psychological readiness for speech communication;
- Ensuring the natural need for them to repeat the language material many times;
- Training students in choosing the right speech variant.

The place of games in a lesson and the time allocated to a game depend on a number of factors of students' preparation, the material being studied, the goals and conditions of the lesson and etc.

How to use games

Games surely are a great fun when played, but still there should be cautions because often they may have adverse effects, for instance, if students got carried away with all the pride of the winner, might say or do something that may hurt feeling of another one. In the moment, games are employed in the lessons, the teacher must bear in mind the control of it in the proper way so not to lose direction of it. The teacher should assure that all the participants enjoy the game and have a pleasant experience, since the classroom should not become a place where students feel stocked in³.

Another important thing to keep in mind is that not all the games are suitable for the classroom environment, or the student's ages and levels. It can be hard to decide which right game is and that is responsibility of the teacher. It is recommended for the teacher to pay attention to the most fundamental criteria of a game; that is a game balanced fun, challenge and learning, for sure⁴.

General Benefits of Games

Games do offer several benefits for students. Below are mentioned some of them according to Casey Melcher⁵.

AFFECTIVE;

- Lowers affective filter
- Promotes communicative competence
- Encourages creative and spontaneous use of language
- Motivates
- Fun

Cognitive;

- Reinforces
- Reviews and extends
- Focuses on grammar communicatively

Recommendations: taking into consideration of the fact that teaching a foreign language requires a lot of effort and time a significant attention should be given to it.

Conclusion

² Passov E.I. Foreign language lesson in secondary school. Moscow; Enlightenment , 1988

³ Chen, I-J 2005. Using games to promote communicative skills in Language learning TESL, P.125-132.

⁴ Tyson A. 2000 How to choose games. The internet TESL Journal , Vol. VII.

⁵ Andrew, W.1984. Games for Language Learning .Cambridge University Press.

Games are best used in the middle or at the end of the lesson to relieve tension. It is important to work with games to bring positive emotions and benefits, and also to serve as an effective incentive when learners' interest or motivation in learning a foreign language starts to diminish. The use of games in foreign personal qualities to preserve and strengthen learning motivation.

REFERENCES:

1. Lukyanchikova N.V. Foreign language teaching at the initial stage of education .//PRIMARY SCHOOL, 2001.
2. Passov E.I. Foreign language lesson in secondary school. Moscow; Enlightenment, 1988.
3. Andrew, W.1984. Games for Language Learning .Cambridge University Press.
4. Chen, I-J 2005. Using games to promote communicative skills in Language learning TESL, P.125-132.
5. Tyson A. 2000 How to choose games. The internet TESL Journal , Vol. VII

